

Studies on the Fixation of Ammonium and Phosphate Ions as Influenced by Organic Matter and Free Oxides of Iron and Aluminium

S. K. BANERJEE

Dept. of Agril. Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswa Vidyalay, Kalyani, Nadia
and

M. SENGUPTA and S. K. GUPTA

University College of Agriculture, Calcutta University

Manuscript received 14 September 1977, accepted 9 January 1980

The effect of organic matter and free oxides of iron and aluminium on the fixation of ammonium and phosphate ions in some soils of West Bengal has been studied. Ammonium fixation decreased and phosphate fixation increased in the organic matter free soils while the reverse was the case in the free oxides removed soils.

AMMONIUM ion when applied as salts of strong acids to soils is rapidly incorporated into the organic and inorganic fractions of the soils and are unavailable to plants. However, the immobilization or fixation of ammonium ions varies with the nature and characteristics of the soils. Per cent clay, nature of clay minerals, exchangeable potassium, amount of organic matter and cation exchange capacity¹⁻⁸ are the most important characteristics affecting the fixation or retention of applied ammonium ions. It has been well established that ammonium fixation in layer silicate minerals takes place by entrapment between adjacent aluminosilicate layers and consequent partial or total collapse of the mineral structure^{2,4}.

When a soluble phosphatic material is added to soil, it reacts with different components of soil and becomes relatively unavailable. Among the various components, iron and aluminium and their free oxides are most important⁹⁻¹². A highly significant correlation has been established¹³ between the amount of phosphate fixed and free iron oxide content in soils. Williams¹⁴ also showed that when active aluminium was removed, the phosphate sorbing power was only about 10 per cent of the original soils, an observation also made by Chu and Sherman¹⁵.

The free oxides of iron and aluminium may be present in films or as a surface coating on the clay particles. Therefore, removal of these oxides may modify the properties of the clay minerals. The present investigation has, therefore, been undertaken with a view to study the effect of organic matter and free iron and aluminium oxides on the fixation of ammonium and phosphate ions in some soils of West Bengal.

Experimental

Ten different soil samples of West Bengal were used for the present investigation. Two acid terai soils from

Alipurduar and Phansidewa belonging to the northern district, two lateritic soils and one red soil from Bankura, Jhargram (Midnapur) and Purulia respectively, one coastal alluvium from Kakdwip (24 Parganas) and four other alluvial soils from Chakdah, Kalyani and Haringhata (Nadia) and Farakka (Murshidabad) were obtained as usual, air dried under shade, ground and sieved through a 0.2 mm sieve. The relevant characteristics of the soils are given in table 1.

The free oxides of iron and aluminium of a part of each soil were removed by the modified method of Mehra and Jackson¹⁶. The free oxide removed samples were then dried, ground and sieved through a 0.2 mm sieve.

Another part of each soil was treated with 6 per cent H₂O₂ to remove the organic matter.

Different soils were then incubated in tubes at 60 per cent moisture holding capacity of the soils at two different incubation periods and subjected to the following treatments. In one set phosphorus was added to the soil in the form of KH₂PO₄ at the rate of 100 ppm of P and in a second set (NH₄)₂SO₄ was added at the rate of 200 ppm of N.

Available phosphate of the soil samples were extracted by Olsen's method and the phosphate content was determined by the colorimetric procedure as described by Jackson¹⁷. The amount of NH₄-N fixed in 15 and 30 days was estimated by the recovery method developed by Bower¹⁸ and Allison *et al*¹⁹.

All estimations were done in duplicate and all the reagents and chemicals used in the present investigation were of A. R. quality.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Soils	pH (1:2:5)	Organic carbon (%)	Clay (%)	c.e.c. me/100gm	Water holding capacity %	Free Fe ₂ O ₃ %	Total P (ppm)	Native fixed NH ₄ ⁺ (ppm)
Alipurduar	5.4	1.600	28.0	8.9	50	0.87	500	176
Phansidewa	4.9	1.550	28.0	8.9	54	1.03	452	165
Bankura	5.6	0.600	20.0	10.2	35	1.82	276	140
Jhargram	5.1	0.435	30.0	7.5	32	2.46	252	149
Purulia	6.8	0.351	16.8	13.2	30	1.50	268	162
Kakdwip	6.0	0.825	70.0	29.2	62	1.66	515	340
Chakdah	6.6	0.800	26.0	31.7	60	1.90	410	326
Farakka	6.1	0.740	57.0	44.1	72	3.13	530	375
Haringhata	7.1	0.750	47.0	16.5	55	2.90	302	320
Kalyani	6.7	1.080	47.0	32.4	52	1.20	—	339

Results and Discussion

The amount of NH₄-N fixed in the soils in two incubation periods are given in table 2. It appears from the result that the fixation of NH₄-N bears a close relation with the clay content of the soils. Kakdwip soil containing higher amount of clay fixed a greater amount than the Bankura and Purulia soils containing comparatively lesser amount (Table 1). The results are in agreement with the findings of Bhaduri *et al*⁸ who showed that the fixation of applied NH₄⁺ bears a significant positive correlation with the clay content of some soils of West Bengal. Table 2 shows that with the increase of the incubation period the fixation does not increase so much indicating that ammonium fixation is a rapid process and maximum fixation (more than 90 per cent) occurs within 15 days.

The amount of NH₄⁺ fixed by organic matter free soils is also given in table 2. As these soils are free from organic matter, the amount of NH₄⁺ fixed depends solely on the amount of clay and the nature of the clay minerals. The results show that the amount of fixation is less than that of the original soils. This may be explained by the fact that hydrogen peroxide when added to the soils destroys the weakly as well as strongly bound native organic matter and in the course of the reaction the H₂O₂ molecule penetrates that lattices of the clays and thereby rupture them. As a result the dimension of the space between the two plates most probably increases and thereby the added NH₄⁺ does not fix so much and can be easily leached out by 1(N)KCl solution. However, the decrease from the control in the fixation of NH₄⁺ in the H₂O₂ treated soils is not so marked. With the increase of the incubation period the fixation in the H₂O₂ treated soils slightly increases. Gupta *et al*²⁰ obtained similar results in some soils of West Bengal.

The results on the fixation of applied NH₄⁺ in the free oxide removed samples are also represented in table 2. It appears that there is a marked increase in the fixation of NH₄⁺ over the control. The results clearly indicate that the presence of free oxides hinders the fixation of NH₄⁺ by clay minerals by blocking the entrance of NH₄⁺ ions between the clay plates. And this is possible if the free oxides form a coating or produce a film on the clay surface. The free oxides or hydrous oxides must have been bonding together surfaces made accessible to NH₄⁺ after their removal. Farakka

TABLE 2—FIXATION OF NH₄-N(ppm) FROM THE ADDED (NH₄)₂SO₄

Soils	Original		Organic matter removed		Free oxide	
	15 days	30 days	15 days	30 days	15 days	30 days
Alipurduar	76.2	79.8	70.5	74.0	83.5	85.2
Phansidewa	70.2	76.2	64.0	66.2	78.2	88.0
Bankura	54.2	59.2	52.0	55.4	63.8	68.2
Jhargram	60.5	66.2	58.2	61.8	71.5	73.2
Purulia	58.6	60.0	56.0	59.8	66.2	66.8
Kakdwip	108.5	119.0	104.6	109.8	119.5	126.5
Farakka	99.2	109.2	96.0	101.4	114.2	122.4
Haringhata	98.0	106.3	96.4	99.8	109.2	118.4
Kalyani	96.0	104.1	95.0	99.8	109.0	113.8
Chakdah	60.2	66.2	55.4	59.0	71.2	79.3

soil containing higher amount of free iron oxides fixes a greater amount of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ after their removal.

The amount of added phosphate fixed in the soils are given in Table 3. The amount of added phosphate fixed is determined by subtracting the amount of phos-

TABLE 3—FIXATION OF ADDED PHOSPHATE (PPM)

Soils	Original		Organic matter removed		Free oxide removed	
	15 days	30 days	15 days	30 days	15 days	30 days
Alipurduar	77.5	74.5	81.4	82.0	53.2	56.5
Phansidewa	74.5	70.0	79.2	83.0	53.4	56.0
Bankura	87.8	91.6	88.0	93.2	63.0	64.0
Jhargram	80.4	83.0	80.6	84.4	56.5	56.8
Purulia	80.6	84.0	80.8	86.0	55.8	56.4
Kakdwip	75.0	78.2	76.2	78.6	55.0	57.2
Chakdah	86.5	88.5	88.0	89.8	63.4	64.0
Farakka	89.6	94.5	90.8	95.5	48.6	48.6
Haringhata	83.5	86.2	84.2	86.4	50.3	50.0
Kalyani	79.5	84.5	80.5	85.6	53.4	54.0

phorus found in the available form from the amount added to the soil. It appears from the data that except in the case of acid soils of Alipurduar and Phansidewa the fixation of phosphate increases with the increase of the incubation period. The fixation of phosphate in the soils under present study may be due to chemical precipitation mainly by ferric and aluminium ions or their free hydrous oxide micelle. Table shows that the fixation of phosphate in the acid soils of Alipurduar and Phansidewa slightly decreases on prolonging the period of incubation. This may be explained by the fact that because of presence of higher amount of organic matter in these two soils microorganisms at the initial stage have multiplied rapidly and a part of the added phosphate has been used up to meet their nutritional requirement. On prolonging the period of incubation the amount of phosphorus fixed has been decreased because the phosphorus fixed in the organic form has gradually been mineralised and with the decomposition of organic matter many organic acids have been produced which solubilise the native fixed phosphorus.

Table 3 also reveals that except in the case of Alipurduar and Phansidewa soils there is a marginal increase in the fixation of phosphate in organic matter free soils in 15 days but on prolonging the period of incubation the fixation also increases. Here also the fixation occurs due to the chemical precipitation mainly by ferric and aluminium ions or their free hydrous oxide

micelle. The higher values of fixation of Alipurduar and Phansidewa soils may be due to the fact that the higher amount of organic matter present in these two soils forms complexes or chelates with Fe and Al. After the removal of organic matter the Fe and Al can easily react with phosphate producing insoluble precipitate.

The amount of added phosphate fixed by the free oxide removed soils at two incubation periods have also been given in table 3. The result shows that there is a considerable decrease in the fixation of phosphate in free oxide removed soils, the maximum decrease being located in the Farakka soil containing higher amount of free oxides. Except the soil of Haringhata all the soils are acidic in reaction (table 1). Fixation of phosphate in acid soils is mainly due to reaction of phosphate with iron and aluminium ions and their free oxides present in the soil. As the free oxides have imparted a great role in phosphate fixation in these soils, their removal has caused a great decrease in phosphate fixation capacity.

References

1. J. B. PAGE and L. D. BAVER, *Proc. Soil. Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1940, 4, 150.
2. J. I. WEAR and J. L. WHITE, *Soil. Sci.*, 1951, 71, 1.
3. F. E. ALLISON, E. M. ROLLER and J. H. DOETSCH, *Soil. Sci.*, 1953, 75, 173.
4. I. BARSHAD, *Soil. Sci.*, 1954, 77, 463.
5. W. D. BURGE and F. E. BROADBENT, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1966, 30, 587.
6. W. C. HINMAN, *Canad. J. Soil Sci.*, 1966, 46, 223.
7. E. OPUWARIBO and C. T. I. ODU, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1975, 26, 350.
8. T. L. BHADURI, S. K. BANERJEE and S. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 822.
9. L. A. DEAN, *Adv. Agron.*, 1949, 1, 391.
10. C. K. RAJAGOPAL and M. A. IDNANI, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1963, 11, 141.
11. J. S. KANWAR, *Soil Sci.*, 1956, 82, 43.
12. S. K. BANERJEE and B. DAS, *Technology*, 1977, 14, 49.
13. E. G. WILLIAMS, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1957, 47, 1533.
14. E. G. WILLIAMS, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1958, 9, 551.
15. A. C. CHU and G. D. SHERMAN, *Hawaii Agric. Exp. Sta. Tech. Bull.*, 1952, 16.
16. O. P. MEHRA and M. L. JACKSON, *Clays and Clay Minerals*, 1958, 7, 317.
17. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis". Prentice-Hall, Inc., Engelwood Cliffs, N. J. 1958.
18. C. A. BOWER, *Soil Sci.*, 1950, 70, 375.
19. F. E. ALLISON, J. H. DOETSCH and E. M. ROLLER, *Soil Sci.*, 1951, 72, 187.
20. S. K. GUPTA, S. K. BANERJEE and A. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 826.